

A Community-driven Collection and Template for DMP Guidance facilitating Data Management across Disciplines and Funding

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Introduction

Data management plans (DMPs) are formal and structured documents that capture all relevant information along the data lifecycle and beyond. A DMP typically describes data handling, archiving, sharing, access, usage and interpretation.

A DMP instance applies a certain DMP template in order to address a specific funder or institution for a given use case. However, the structure of existing DMP templates is often designed for funder's requirements and is consequently generic in scope to address diverse research projects and communities. Thus, these templates often lack guidance on how to structure discipline-specific information in a DMP and information on related consequences, when not following recommended steps. Moreover, additional guidance is often provided in consultations or as unstructured text in specific DMP tools or separate documents and is therefore not prepared for discovery or reuse.

To address these challenges, we propose to structure DMP guidance by applying a pattern concept. The pattern concept² was developed to collect proven solutions for frequently occurring problems. First patterns covered architecture elements, like specific window forms for specific house forms. By now, the pattern concept is well-established in several disciplines, in particular as software design patterns³ tackling frequently occurring IT problems and providing solution blueprints.

A pattern provides a structure to describe the mentioned pair of problem and solution. Thus, a pattern describes the problem, the tested solution, requirements, which link problem and solution, the context, the rationale, and the pragmatics of the provided problem and solution. Moreover, a pattern is contextualized, i.e. the described problem occurs in a specific context or the solution can only be applied in specific context. Several patterns can therefore describe different solutions for the same problem in different contexts.

Patterns are typically shipped in collections, e.g. with a certain thematic or technical focus. With the help of the given pattern structure - the pattern attributes - users are enabled to search/filter a collection for patterns that fit to their use case(s).

The overall aims of the pattern concept are facilitating reuse of established / well-known solutions (best practices), collection and exchange of knowledge and experiences. Thus, such a pattern concept - providing a generic and common structure for describing problems and solutions - serves as the basis for our proposed guidance pattern template.

With our proposed DMP guidance template, we provide a common structure for DMP guidance facilitating (1) DMP writing across disciplines, (2) the provision of concrete examples (best practices), and (3) the provision of consequences to foster awareness for certain data management topics.

In the next section, we describe the general proposed structure for describing DMP guidance as patterns, which can be used to develop further patterns. We then discuss a community-driven collection of patterns in an open repository and provide selected examples covering common or disciplinary DMP guidance pattern examples. Each of the described pattern examples is based on needs, experiences, or implementations from existing research projects supported by the document's authors.

² Alexander C, Ishikawa S, Silverstein M, et al (1977) A Pattern Language. Oxford University Press, New York.

³ Gamma E, Helm R, Johnson R, Vlissides J (1995) Design Patterns: Elements of Reusable Object-Oriented Software. Addison Wesley Professional Computing Series.

Guidance Pattern Template

Our proposed DMP guidance template is built on the software design pattern concept. To meet relevant requirements for DMP-related activities, we adapted several characteristics (pattern attributes) facilitating a structured management and discovery of guidance information for specific use cases and disciplines. The following list provides attribute names and brief descriptions:

Guidance name *

A descriptive and unique name that helps in identifying and referring to the guidance pattern

Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance *

The goal behind the guidance pattern and the reason for using it

Recommended activities *

A description of what should be implemented and how.

Example / Use case

An exemplary scenario in which this guidance pattern can be used.

Context

The situation in which the guidance pattern is usable including information about (see detailed explanations below):

disciplines

funder

templates

keywords (see below)

(Rationale)

A sound justification for the recommended guidance.

Consequences / Costs

A description of the results, side effects, and trade-offs caused by using the guidance pattern.

Literature

Further readings relevant for the guidance pattern, including best practices, detailed guidance documents.

(Participants)

(A listing of roles involved in the recommended activities)

Related guidance

Further related guidance pattern(s), e.g. a similar or dependent/required pattern.

Characteristics marked with * are mandatory, describing either name, problem or solution. The other characteristics are optional and should be described if useful.

To describe the context of the pattern, we propose the following initial list of potential keywords. The list is based on consultation and project experiences of the authors and is meant to be extended, if needed. Since the keywords support discovery, sorting, and filtering of patterns, we suggest either describing the relevant disciplines as well as data collection methods, and major data / project properties:

- *Disciplines: To provide a commonly tagged list of patterns, we propose to choose one or more relevant disciplines from the DFG subject area list⁴. If the pattern is relevant for several disciplines, it should be tagged as **generic***
- *Type of data: We suggest to select the type of data for the created data of the pattern use case*
 - *observational data*
 - *audio-visual data*
 - *textual data*

⁴ https://www.dfg.de/en/dfg_profile/statutory_bodies/review_boards/subject_areas/index.jsp

- *experimental data*
- *simulation data*
- *derived data*
- *Collection methods: The method on how to collect data strongly relates to data processing solutions and privacy/security aspects. We suggest to choose from the following list*
 - *interview*
 - *field observation*
 - *simulation*
 - *archival work*
 - *survey*
 - *experimental measurement*
 - *web harvesting*
 - *crowd sourcing / citizen science*
 - *secondary data collection (re-use of existing datasets)*
- *Project properties: The project properties can relate to specific guidance, e.g. big data can only be published in certain repositories; industry collaboration sometimes requires embargo times. However, we propose to use major / relevant project properties, if needed, e.g.*
 - *personal / sensitive data*
 - *big data*
 - *industry collaboration*
 - *clinical data*

Community-driven Collection in an open Repository

To provide expert knowledge for data management and specific guidance, we propose the community-driven collection and quality-assurance of guidance patterns. We therefore provide an open repository for DMP guidance patterns that facilitate experts in adding new patterns, updating patterns, e.g. with new best practice project examples, and commenting existing patterns.

https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/metadastandardsandcommons/dmp_guidance_pattern⁵

The concept of providing supplementary information to generic DMP templates in a modular way is not new. For instance, the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) developed a guidance for recurring template topics⁶ and institutions can provide further guidance for their users within DCC's DMPonline by grouping their recommendations and best practices according to the DMP themes. However, with our DMP pattern concept and the provided repository, we foster reusing condensed and harmonized guidance and examples by linking from DMP tools, like RDMO⁷, or other related knowledge bases. Moreover, we enable an update mechanism for guidance that is independent from the linked DMP tool by separating DMP tool and guidance information management. Thus, we support domain experts that are not familiar with specific DMP tools syntax to provide their guidance or comments via open GitLab repository as structured text.

By using the GitLab issue tracking, we enable commenting patterns and envision a community-driven update and quality-assurance process, similar to the Wiki approach.

Future work will improve the guidance pattern discovery, e.g. by using the given tagging/classification and linking the repository to discovery tools.

⁵ The repository is publicly available. DFN AAI can be used for login. For support, please contact the corresponding author.

⁶ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/publications/DMP-themes.pdf>

⁷ Research Data Management organiser: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>

Pattern Examples

In this chapter, we provide several disciplinary pattern examples and show how to apply the guidance pattern template for generic patterns.

Examples for Earth System Sciences Guidance

Table 1: User-friendly and efficient managing of geodata in a metadata catalogue

Name	Example
Guidance name	User-friendly and efficient managing of geodata in a metadata catalogue for geodata
Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance	<p>Managing geodata can be challenging, in particular, when a huge number of (big) spatial datasets should be made available for collaborated usage/processing or should be findable within and outside projects. To find / discover geodata, users need specific interfaces that foster spatial, and combined temporal and thematic filtering. Further, to evaluate the fitness for use of potential geodata, users often need a map-based visualisation.</p> <p>Metadata catalogues for geodata provide user interfaces, a related database, and (often) a standardised interface to manage and discover metadata and geodata, and implement a role and access management. They are either implemented and published as open-source products and can be configured/modified/extended or are available as commercial solution.</p>
Recommended activities	<p>In Earth System Sciences, Geo-(metadata) catalogues are used to manage geospatial data and related metadata by providing discipline-specific user interfaces, e.g. spatial filter and search menus, and APIs, e.g. for spatial requests.</p> <p>Manage geospatial data in a metadata catalogue for geodata directly from the project beginning. Whenever possible, use an existing catalogue, e.g. an institutional catalogue.</p> <p>When not having the option to use an existing catalogue, you can choose from a list of various existing (open-source) catalogues.</p>
Example / Use case	<p>The BMBF project GeoKur aims to support the curation and quality assurance of Earth System Science (ESS) data sets, focusing on the suitability of geospatial time-series of global land use data by analysing human-environment relations such as land degradation, biodiversity, human migration and ecosystem services.</p> <p>The project⁸ uses existing publicly available datasets and provides produced datasets as open data, open access, and FAIR-compliant. During the project, datasets will be managed via open source catalogue CKAN with spatial extensions facilitating direct metadata and data access via API. Selected results will be stored in the institutional data management platform DMP/DRP including raw data after the project ends, resp. published on PANGAEA for long-term storage.</p> <p>The researchers develop data analysis scripts using the language R. Scripts will be managed on GitHub and published via Zenodo following</p>

⁸ Egli, Lukas, Fischer, Julia, Groth, Juliane, Della Chiesa, Stefano, & Henzen, Christin. (2022). Data Management Plan for Use Cases of the GeoKur Project on suitability of global land use data to assess relationships between land use, degradation, pollination and human migration. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5992729>

reproducible research approaches by including links to the well-documented open-source GitHub repository and used datasets.

The data management focus of the project is on discipline-specific provenance and quality tracking for produced datasets and documentation for both - collected and produced - datasets. Therefore, all datasets will be described using a project-specific GeoDCAT metadata profile with linked PROV-O and Data Quality Vocabulary. Metadata in the GeoDCAT format will therefore be automatically extracted or tracked by GeoKur-specific tools or extended by manual processes, when extraction or tracking is not possible. A specific quality register facilitates the curated management of quality measure descriptions.

Checklist for choosing a catalogue in GeoKur:

- Options for managing private and public datasets
- Open-source, strong community, high number of extensions, several active instances available on the Web
- Options to manage discipline-specific metadata profile, here a project-specific GeoDCAT profile with extended provenance and quality information for geospatial datasets
- Options to implement several metadata profiles, here for datasets, workflows and processes
- Geospatial filter and extent visualisation
- Options to manage different types of data, geospatial and non-spatial data
- API to directly create, update or delete metadata and data via R scripts
- Interface to link project-specific and institutional catalogue
- Options to link the catalogue with existing geospatial Web services, e.g. OGC WMS visualization services

Context	
Discipline	Earth System Sciences or related disciplines mainly using geospatial data
Funder	Not relevant for this guidance
Template	Science Europe, Section 5 - Data sharing
Keywords	
Consequences / Costs	When not using a metadata catalogue for geodata, data discovery and data usage will be limited and inefficient, in particular spatial filtering, search, and API-based data and metadata usage or update, e.g. in analysis scripts. Catalogues for geodata provide specific filter, search and preview functionality for geospatial dataset. When not using a catalogue, datasets have to be indexed/tagged with the spatial extent with other tools or manually. For the evaluation of fitness for use, the data needs to be downloaded, if Web-based preview functionality is not provided. Furthermore, metadata catalogues for geodata provide specific interfaces to automatically publish and update data in geospatial Web services, which allows researchers to use the catalogue for geodata as a central entry point for managing and publishing data. Thus, when not using a metadata catalogue for geodata, data publication in such Web services needs to be done as separate step.
Literature	Open-Source Catalogue for Geodata GeoNetwork

	<p>https://geonetwork-opensource.org/ Open-Source Catalogue with several geospatial extensions</p> <p>https://ckan.org/ Open Geospatial Consortium – Description of Catalogue Services</p> <p>https://www.ogc.org/standards/cat Scientific geodata infrastructures: challenges, approaches and directions</p> <p>https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17538947.2013.781244 Handbook of Research on Geoinformatics, Chapter 5: Spatial Data Infrastructures</p> <p>https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/book/470</p>
Participants	Data manager, IT team
Related guidance	Metadata profiling for geospatial data; Open geospatial formats

Table 2: Sharing large-volume Earth System Science-simulation datasets by adopting and extending pre-existing (meta)data standards

Name	Example
Guidance name	Sharing large-volume Earth System Science-simulation datasets by adopting and extending pre-existing (meta)data standards
Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance	Coupled Earth System Model (ESM) simulations to study the paleoclimate are very computationally intensive (spanning up to 100ky of simulation time) and technically demanding and can therefore usually only be carried out once. The challenge in the next step is sharing the very large amount of data for efficient reuse by the global community.
Recommended activities	<p>As it is out-of-scope and also impractical to make all output generated by extensive ESM simulations available for global reuse, the first recommended activity is to define a clear subset of the data to be made available. This includes deciding on a parameter set (usually standard parameters such as Essential Climate Variables⁹ (ECVs)) and on the temporal resolution of the output to be shared. This process requires close and collegial communication between project-scientists and RDM support staff.</p> <p>If domain-specific and globally accepted (meta)data standards already exist, it has to be decided if it is suitable to apply these. If necessary, adaption/extension of existing standards may be required.</p> <p>Data publication and dissemination is done via a chosen repository or data service suitable for making the data globally available to the global community in an efficient manner. Consequently, the above decisions on the data amount to be shared must also take the mid- to long-term storage resources required and realistically available into account.</p>
Example / Use case	The PalMod project ¹⁰ aims at conducting fully-coupled Earth System Model (ESM) simulations covering the time span of the last entire glacial cycle (130ky). Such efforts are unprecedented and it is expected that the simulation output by PalMod will be of very high interest to the global climate science community. Therefore, the PalMod project has

⁹<https://public.wmo.int/en/programmes/global-climate-observing-system/essential-climate-variables>

¹⁰ <https://www.palmod.de>

made the global dissemination of the generated model output a specific project task.

PalMod data will be made available via the domain-specific ESGF¹¹ infrastructure. For publication in ESGF, data have to be standardised to ensure findability in the global catalogue and disk storage resources have to be provided for by the project.

For PalMod, the subset of the data to be published was defined in close and intense collaboration with the project scientists. The standardisation of the data is performed at DKRZ and builds on the experience gained in previous projects, e.g. CMIP¹². The existing (meta)data standards had to be extended because fully-coupled ESMs produce output not previously considered in any other contexts.

Long-term storage and curation of the PalMod data will be achieved via the WDCC¹³, the FAIR-enabling and certified domain-specific long-term archive hosted at DKRZ.

Context

- Discipline Earth System Sciences or related disciplines mainly using geospatial data
 - Funder Not relevant for this guidance
 - Template Science Europe, Section 5 - Data sharing
 - Keywords
-

Consequences / Costs

Without dedicated efforts, flagship climate model simulations would be very difficult to make available to the global community in an efficient manner and would ultimately be lost, possibly resulting in loss of knowledge and an incredible waste of public resources.

Achieving the full-featured RDM services on a project-level as done in PalMod requires funding for dedicated staff. The experience from PalMod shows that funding of 1.5 FTEs over the duration of the project is just enough to cope with the work involved.

Funding of dedicated hardware is also essential for projects in which the anticipated total (practically irreproducible) data volume is on the order of 10s of PBs.

Literature

Cinquini, L., et al. ,2014, The Earth System Grid Federation: An open infrastructure for access to distributed geospatial data, *Future Gener. Comp. Sy.*, 36, 400–417, doi:10.1016/j.future.2013.07.002.

Williams, Dean N., et al. ,2016, A Global Repository for Planet-Sized Experiments and Observations, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 97, 5 (2016): 803-816, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-15-00132.1>

Wilkinson, M. D., et al., 2016, The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, *Sci. Data*, 3, 1–9, doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

<http://www.copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/>

Taylor, Karl E., et al. "CMIP5 data reference syntax (DRS) and controlled vocabularies." PCMDI: San Francisco Bay Area, CA, USA (2011).

Meinshausen, M., et al. (2011). The paleoclimate modeling intercomparison project contribution to CMIP5. *WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project-Phase 5-CMIP5*, 16, 15-51.

¹¹ <https://esgf.llnl.gov>

¹² <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>

¹³ <https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/ceraresearch/>

	Pronk, T. E., 2019, The time efficiency gain in sharing and reuse of research data, <i>Data Sci. J.</i> , 18, 10, doi:10.5334/dsj-2019-010.
Participants	Data Stewards; Researchers
Related guidance	

Example for Sociology Guidance

Table 3: Transfer and storage of highly sensitive interview data in social sciences

Name	Example
Guidance name	Transfer and storage of highly sensitive interview data in social sciences
Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance	Interviewees and associated persons must be able to expect confidentiality and security of their interviews and related information. Sensitive Data collected in the field have to be transferred via secure connections to secure systems. Data on field equipment is securely deleted without sacrificing data needed for research.
Recommended activities	<p>During preparation of the field studies, the project team should set up a detailed data security plan to identify potential risks, obstacles, and possible solutions.</p> <p>Project members and local data security experts have to evaluate hardware and software options as well as procedures in the field for security and practicality. The approved methodology and technical solution can then serve as standard setting for the project.</p>
Example / Use case	<p>A research project examined practices, structures, and communication within partially closed social groups by interviewing selected groups. Activities and opinions of these group members were also potentially of interest to judicial authorities in the country the groups reside in. An impact assessment on data protection was performed for each of the interviewed groups and each topic. The identified risks for the interviewees were then used to determine the required minimal security measures and to provide them to the interviewees before conducting the interviews to allow for a broadly informed judgement. The interviews took place in premises familiar to the interviewees. Audio files were recorded with dictation devices; as far as technically possible, the recordings were directly stored on the device in encrypted form. Afterwards, the data was transferred to an encrypted hidden container on the local hard drive. The recording device was formatted after checking the successful copy.</p> <p>The promptly pseudonymized transcripts and logs (text files) were uploaded to an encrypted cloud storage, physically located in the EU. After successful completion of the upload, the encrypted data were deleted from the notebooks.</p> <p>As far as possible, the codes / keys underlying the pseudonymization were determined prior to the interviews (for places, groups, events, ...). The pseudonymization keys were stored separately in security cabinets. Researchers analysed the data exclusively at the research institute. Data was only temporarily stored on workstation computers during processing and analysis.</p>
Context	
- Discipline	Social Sciences

- Funder	Not relevant for this guidance
- Template	Science Europe, Section 3b and 4a
- Keywords	sensitive data; interview; data transfer; storage;
Consequences / Costs	<p>Proper impact assessment and determination / selection of required security measures has to be done carefully and thus, incur personnel cost. Furthermore, increased security settings often require financial investments, e.g. storage services, specific hard- and software. Inadequate measures can lead to data leaks that expose sensitive data. This can have consequences under data protection laws. Even more serious are the possible negative effects on the subjects. Beyond the potential risks to individuals and groups, the willingness of potential subjects to cooperate with the researchers will suffer. In addition, data leaks that are made public shake confidence in research as a whole and can thus hamper research efforts in the long term and beyond the project.</p>
Literature	<p>RatSWD [German Data Forum] (2020): Data collection using new information technology Recommendations on data quality, data management, research ethics, and data protection RatSWD Output 6 (6) Berlin: German Data Forum (RatSWD) https://doi.org/10.17620/02671.51 RatSWD [German Data Forum] (2020): Data Protection Guide. 2nd fully revised edition. RatSWD Output 8 (6). Berlin, German Data Forum. https://doi.org/10.17620/02671.57. Forschungsdatenmanagement sozialwissenschaftlicher Umfragedaten (in German), https://doi.org/10.3224/84742233</p>
Participants	Researchers; local or institutional computer centre
Related guidance	<p>Backup and storage Legal and ethical</p>

Examples for Multidisciplinary Guidance

Table 4: Use of controlled vocabularies

Name	Example
Guidance name	Use of controlled vocabularies
Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance	The scientific community should be able to understand data, metadata, and associated documentation unambiguously. This requires the use of unambiguous names for entities / concepts with precisely determined meanings / definitions (vocabulary).
Recommended activities	<p>Determine the classes of entities, relations, and concepts that will appear in the dataset. For each class, evaluate which controlled vocabularies can be used. The vocabularies should (1) ideally be common in your field, (2) provide sufficiently detailed terms (e.g. standardized names for all relevant geographical places, personal entries for African mathematicians, chemical compounds, proteins etc.), and (3) be expected to be freely long-term accessible. Preferably, the vocabulary uses unique identifiers for each entry.</p> <p>Ensure that the vocabularies are used consistently throughout the project. If possible and needed, try to extend the vocabulary by new concepts. This usually requires an intermediary.</p>
Example / Use case	<p><i>Example from Geo-Linguistics:</i></p> <p>The project VerbaAlpina investigates the lexic of dialects spoken in the Alpine region in their cultural and historic context. They use different digital and analog data sources. Moreover, a diverse set of typical data sources such as dictionaries and linguistic atlases are combined and enriched with information contributed by third parties via social software (“crowdsourcing”). The resulting geo-linguistic database allows for the application of modern digital analysis and visualisation methods.</p> <p>The data combines a large amount of georeferenced individual records. VerbaAlpina classified each record according to the designated concept, the morpholexical type and the etymological origin. All records are georeferenced at the level of the political municipalities within the perimeter of the Alpine convention. Each concept, morpholexical type and municipality has a unique internal identifier.</p> <p>Wherever possible, the internal IDs are mapped to identifiers in established controlled vocabularies. In particular, WikiData records and the corresponding QIDs (for concepts) and LIDs (for words/designations) are assigned to VerbaAlpina items. An example would be the QID Q1432579, which refers to the concept of an “alpine dairy”. Another example from the field of designations would be the LID L643765, pointing to the French lexeme “chalet”. In the long-term, gaps in WikiData, where precise terms do not yet exist, can be closed by adding additional entities.</p> <p>The Glottolog vocabulary is used to specify languages and the Geonames vocabulary identifies parishes and regions. Cases where the location cannot be described via a Geoname entry are not uncommon. Here the unique language-independent identification relies primarily on precise geo-coordinates. Wherever possible, ORCIDs and / or GND identifiers refer to persons involved in the project.</p>

Further, an identification of morpholexical types using entities of the GND vocabulary with the entity class "letters, morphemes, words and objects of linguistic studies" is considered.

For details see here: <https://www.verba-alpina.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/?p=16972> and https://www.verba-alpina.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/?page_id=493&db=212&letter=N#114.

Context	
- Discipline	Generic; Examples from: Linguistics, Geosciences
- Funder	Not relevant for this guidance
- Template	Science Europe
Consequences / Costs	<p>Without applying controlled vocabularies, (automated) use of the data is only possible with additional preparatory work.</p> <p>When not using controlled vocabularies, humans and machines can misinterpret the data due to the use of ambiguous terms. For example, the term "inclusion" is usually assigned different meanings in geology, mathematics, and sociology. Here, the explicit description of the corresponding concepts and link to persistent identifiers such as WikiData QIDs can help clarify such ambiguities.</p> <p>Language-dependent data, e.g., codes, and classifications for text passages, is harder to process and understand, if the used vocabulary does not support multiple languages or cannot easily be mapped to other controlled vocabularies.</p> <p>Consequently using controlled vocabularies requires an initial time of investment. However, once suitable vocabularies have been identified and utilised, they can be reused in following projects.</p>
Literature	<p>DDI Working Paper Series - Best Practices, No.5, DDI Alliance, 2009, http://dx.doi.org/10.3886/DDIBestPractices05</p> <p>Introduction to Controlled Vocabularies: Terminology for Art, Architecture, and Other Cultural Works. Patricia Harpring. Getty Publications, revised edition, 2013, (digital version of the 2010 edition: https://www.getty.edu/publications/virtuallibrary/160606018X.html)</p>
Participants	Researchers, Data curators
Related guidance	Documentation

Table 5: Use of unique identifiers for diverse, highly granular data

Name	Example
Guidance name	Use of unique identifiers for diverse, highly granular data
Motivation / Intent / Aim of guidance	Metadata and data need to be unambiguously referenced by unique identifiers throughout the research process, in particular in collaborative research. This addresses sub sets of datasets as well as individual data records.
Recommended activities	Identifiers can facilitate identifying both - data and metadata. Researchers should consider what level of granularity is useful, e.g. if referring to a logical subsets of datasets or pointing to a specific feature is needed. In those cases, an identifier (ID) should be assigned to the dataset and all identified sub sets / features at an early stage. This

simplifies referencing the dataset and tracking the provenance of aggregated datasets. Ideally, the body / system that assigns the identifiers has to provide unique IDs and allows for assigning basal metadata to the ID.

In addition to being used for referencing a dataset, IDs can also be assigned to instruments, for instance. Metadata of instruments do not change over time. Thus, reusing the once provided metadata by linking to a unique identifiers fosters efficient research and, in particular reduces efforts in metadata management.

ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium) provides a useful system to assign IDs and to manage instruments. In this way, it facilitates reproducibility.

A published dataset should always be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), a common persistent identifier.

Example / Use case

The first example is provided by the project VerbaAlpina, which investigated the lexic of dialects spoken in the Alpine region in their cultural and historic context. Different digital and analogue data sources were used. A diverse set of classical data sources such as dictionaries and linguistic atlases was combined and enriched with information contributed by third parties via social approaches ("crowdsourcing"). The resulting geo-linguistic database allows for the application of modern digital analysis and visualisation methods. Analogue data sources were digitised and transcribed in a specific Web-based user interface following a standardised workflow. Data that was already available digitally was automatically transformed to the central data format. All harmonized dataset contained detailed geo-references in addition to linguistic information. The dataset was composed of thousands of individual records. New records are added regularly, so that the common harmonized dataset grows in the long term.

For details: <https://www.verba-alpina.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/?p=16972&db=212> and https://www.verba-alpina.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/?page_id=493&db=212.

During the collection phase, a unique project-internal identifier has been assigned to each individual record. When the datasets were imported into the institutional archive (UB Discover¹⁴), a locally managed persistent identifier (LMU-ID - maintained and curated by the university library) - that is included in the record metadata - was automatically assigned each record (at all levels of granularity)

For each published version of the VerbaAlpina dataset, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is also assigned via DataCite. Individual records and predetermined classes of sub sets can be referenced by the local identifier.

Moreover, the repository's request function allows researchers to assign a DOI on the fly to a record they want to cite / use.

¹⁴ <https://discover.ub.uni-muenchen.de/catalog/?f%5BcollectionStr%5D%5B%5D=VerbaAlpina>

The second example comes from the engineering sciences, more specifically from thermodynamics. In this field, experiments are mainly carried out on instruments and/or self-built devices. The working group has more than 30 different instruments or self-built devices, which are usually shared by several scientific assistants. The instruments and self-built apparatus vary in size. This size can be an important parameter, considering the sometimes prevailing space shortage at universities.

When experiments are carried out, analogue data such as data on the installation of the sample or observation data is sometimes created, but mostly digital data is generated by measuring the samples using specific instruments. These instruments generate metadata for the measurements, which are automatically or manually filled with the corresponding values. At the same time, these instruments or self-built apparatuses have constant metadata such as the location, the serial number, the person responsible for the instrument, the software, the list of metadata output, etc. This metadata is an important factor in the reproducibility of the results and must therefore be managed and provided to the researchers. However, it does not have to be stored by each co-worker, because the values / characteristics are do not change over time. Therefore, the working group decided to assign persistent identifiers in the form of an ePIC for each instrument.

The stored metadata include the location, the serial number of the instrument, the manufacturer's name, what kind of measurements can be carried out, the person responsible for the instrument, the related software, the version of the software, automatically and manually created metadata, the instrument description, and the reference/link to the manuals.

Context	
- Discipline	(geo)linguistics, engineering
- Funder	Not relevant for this guidance
- Template	Science Europe, Section 5d
Consequences / Costs	Without persistent identifiers and the associated long-term maintenance of the landing page and resolving of the PID, published / accessible research objects, like datasets or instruments, are at risk of link rot (failure of hyperlinks / URL to point to their intended target): references to the research objects can no longer be checked and the research objects can no longer be found. This might reduces the trustworthiness of the resulting data in the eyes of potential downstream users.
Literature	Stocker et al., https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2020-018/ Results of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Working group on Persistent Identifiers for Instruments: https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2020-018/
Participants	Researchers
Related guidance	